

Open Data Processing for the Argentine Research Network

Problems of open data processing in Argentina's largest research network:

- Although Argentina has [some public and open research computing infrastructure](#), its access **is yet to be democratized** to all the researchers who need processing power, but do not have a strong computer science background or access to that scarce talent.
- Currently, the program for accessing Argentina's public research network of computing infrastructure is highly competitive. It **lacks a welcoming community, training, or technical support** to ease the process of going from a single computer to a cluster, which is not trivial ([Carnota, 2024](#)). For example, Argentina has no shared environments for remote collaboration with code and data.
- Using computing **infrastructure** outside Argentina is often not feasible for research because data **must follow national regulations** regarding privacy and data sharing. We experienced this challenge firsthand working with [ARPHAI](#) and [The Catalyst Project](#).

Aims: Our project, the first of its kind from and for Argentina, will tackle these problems by:

1. Creating an on-ramp to high-performing computing (HPC) service of cloud computing [JupyterHubs](#) and [Notebooks](#) within the largest Argentine research organization network.
2. Building a welcoming community of practice around this service with community-led governance and [restorative justice community guidelines](#) (aka, code of conduct)..
3. Training in best open data storage and processing practices to low-resourced research environments, including training trainers to exponentially maximize our project's impact.

Impact and success metrics: At the end of the third year, 150 researchers at 40 research orgs with the least access to open data and cloud computing services in Argentina will:

1. Go from single computer or small local cluster users to users of collaborative Jupyter tools.
2. Learn best HPC practices, increasing reproducibility ([Cholias et al, 2020](#)).
3. Receive coaching to publish at least one FAIR open dataset. Researchers who have already published data will increase the number of datasets published.
4. Join a friendly, supportive community for open data publishing and processing.
5. Become certified trainers with the ability to effectively train and coach others on these topics, multiplying this project's impact for years to come.

This project will also: **1. Conduct** an ethically approved, pre-registered, **mixed research study** and publish it openly; **2. Increase sustainability** by, for example, tripling the researchers (from 20% to 60%) who adequately budget central computing services in their funding requests; and **3. Improve the network governance** for this service to scale it to the whole Argentine computing infrastructure for research.

This project aligns with the five objectives of the IOI Fund for Network Adoption:

1. **Increases access to open content** by offering an open cloud infrastructure service to a network of 40 research organizations. The service will require researchers to publish data analyzed with this service in [Argentina's open data repository network](#).
2. **Advances collaborative research on critical global issues** because we will select participating organizations for this service from those researching topics that address pressing global challenges (e.g., climate, agriculture, health).
3. **Offers a sustainable and community-driven infrastructure** by improving community participation in its governance and ensuring continuity of the service beyond this funding.
4. **Ensures a fair and accessible research ecosystem:** A. We will prioritize research organizations with the least historical access to cloud computing and open data

publishing; B. MetaDocencia will apply its [Accessibility Policy](#) to make this project as universally inclusive as possible; C. MetaDocencia’s team will use its over 30 years of experience navigating North-South collaborations in this project. We will also potentiate South-South collaborations by openly publishing this project’s training materials and all other resources, leveraging [our extended network](#), so that organizations from the Global Majority (e.g., LABI, CABANANet) can reuse this project’s outputs.

5. **Strengthens Argentina’s largest research network as a shared infrastructure provider by** generating a community of practice and accessible open training.

Timeline (see Budget for more details)	Y1				Y2				Y3			
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
Project launch and wrap-up												
Research study & project impact measurement												
Beta Jupyter service (piloting and improvement)												
Jupyter service in production												
Community building (40 network research orgs)												
Iterative co-creation of open training materials												
Training and coaching (150 researchers)												
Train the trainer (30 certified trainees)												
Community-driven network governance 2.0												
Project future sustainability												

Feasibility: [MetaDocencia](#) (MD) and [UNC Supercómputo](#) (UNC) are uniquely positioned to bring this project to fruition. MD brings extensive experience in community-centered open science [training](#) across Latin America. Over the past five years, we have delivered 94 training editions to over 1,500 researchers from 33 countries, conducted five train-the-trainer programs, with a [Net Promoter Score](#) of 89% (a score >80% reflects world-class service). For more MD impact, see [this infographic](#). UNC has been part of and provided research computing services since 2010 to a network of >300 Argentine research organizations, the largest research organization network in the country. [In 2023 alone](#), we served 273 researchers from more than 40 research organizations who published over 150 academic papers that relied on our shared computing resources.

Sustainability: We will ensure this project's sustainability beyond this proposal by: 1. Proactively seeking partnerships with key stakeholders, including private corporations, philanthropic organizations (e.g., CZI, Pew Trust, Gates Foundation), and regional financial institutions (e.g., Development Banks of Latin America and the Caribbean, Inter-American Development Bank); 2. Training the community to triple the researchers who adequately budget data and computing infrastructure so that fee-for-service becomes a more reliable source of income for this service; and 3. Disseminating our research findings in Argentina’s policy-making fora to inform national research funding.

Community engagement: UNC is part of and has been serving [CONICET](#), the most extensive research organization network in Argentina, [with over 300 research organizations](#), for 15 years. During the project launch, we will explore UNC’s usage records to assess who within

the network can benefit more from additional computing resources. We will also reach out to the whole network with a mixed (i.e., qualitative and quantitative) study of their data and computing services needs. This research will enable us to optimize our work to meet the community's specific needs, delivering significant impact for the research organizations that have been systematically underserved with data and computing services. Following the project's onboarding, we will engage the community through synchronous trainings, coaching, and gatherings, while stewarding an asynchronous dedicated and secure space for knowledge sharing (e.g., Zulip), and leveraging MetaDocencia's and UNC's robust communication channels.

Challenges and mitigation strategies. We have identified two main challenges:

1. Research organizations with large amounts of data will struggle with low data transfer speed to the UNC cloud because Argentina is not an active RedCLARA member due to political instability. **Mitigations:** We will work with the research communities to find technical solutions for data transfer needs and continue our current policy work at the national level so that Argentina becomes an active RedCLARA member.
2. Argentinean researchers at organizations with the lowest access to cloud infrastructure face heavy workloads and highly precarious conditions often without time for engaging in research or training. **Mitigation:** Although having access to this infrastructure will ease their workloads, we have also budgeted symbolic honoraria to incentivize and help protect the time participants will need to dedicate to research and training.

Experience with shared infrastructure: Envisioning to improve computing infrastructure hosted in Argentina, MD and UNC joined forces in 2022 via [The Catalyst Project](#). This 2i2c-led pilot project provided cloud infrastructure for researchers in Africa and Latin America. In Catalyst, MD recruited and trained Latin American communities while UNC seconded the infrastructure implementation for two years. However, this infrastructure was often hosted outside the researchers' country, limiting the data researchers could process. This proposal is a natural evolution of Catalyst. MD and UNC, with deep knowledge of Argentina's research environment and experience serving Argentina's most extensive research network, will apply what we have learned to ensure success and mitigate risks.

Community governance: UNC has a [formal governance structure](#) where CONICET's network votes on infrastructure use through CCT-CONICET Córdoba, the local representative of the network. UNC resource governance is outstanding nationally due to the solidarity principles it applies. For example, UNC prioritizes PhD students nearing defense for service usage; full servers dedicated to the network requests (e.g., [Ollama](#) local instance to run [Tango-70b](#), open generative AI tuned to Argentina); or prioritizing [researchers at an organization affected by catastrophic flooding](#). [MD has openly built its community-driven governance](#) and [assisted LABI in designing its own](#). In this project, the community research study and MD experience will allow us to increase community participation in UNC governance formally.

Commitment to open research infrastructure: MD has published [academic articles](#), pre-registered [open research work](#), [datasets, code, and reports](#), including over [200 resources](#) and a transparent [website](#). By [contextualizing NASA's Open Science 101](#) and creating an [open-access glossary](#), MD ensured Latin America's representation in global open science. UNC uses exclusively open-source software (e.g., Linux, Spack) and tools (e.g., Zulip, GitLab) for all its operations and is a frequent contributor for the FLOSS community, particularly for HPC packages (e.g., 42 commits for [Spack, including the maintenance of Spack's package UCC](#)).